

Implications of Hawking Activities on the Kumasi Campus of University of Education, Winneba

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Author's contribution

The sole author designed, analyzed and interpreted and prepared the manuscript.

Article Information

DOI: 10.9734/BJESBS/2017/33356

Editor(s):

(1) Eduardo Montero Garcia, Department of Electromechanical Engineering, Polytechnic School, University of Burgos, Spain.

Reviewers:

(1) Jia Yu, Christopher Newport University, USA.

(2) Adetoro Rasheed Adenrele, Federal College of Education, Abeokuta, Nigeria.

(3) Syamsir, Padang State University, Indonesia.

Complete Peer review History: <http://www.sciencedomain.org/review-history/19114>

Original Research Article

Received 11th April 2017

Accepted 12th May 2017

Published 18th May 2017

ABSTRACT

Street vending or hawking has become an important economic activity highly patronized by persons with limited educational and professional training especially in developing countries. It is characterized by traders transforming public spaces originally unintended for trading purposes into arena of economic activities. The practice has not only found itself in the central business district of major cities and towns but in religious places, educational institutions, offices and lorry parks. This study sought to examine hawking activities and their implications on an educational institution, namely the Kumasi Campus of University of Education, Winneba, Ghana. Using a descriptive study design, structured questionnaires were administered to 60 respondents who were selected randomly. Data obtained from the field were analysed using descriptive statistics. The findings revealed that hawkers ($m=1.03$, $\pm SD=.158$) plied their trade along the stretch of road leading to Faculty Block particularly in the afternoon and dealt in various categories of goods with sachet water being mostly sold. Respondents ($m=4.50$, $\pm SD=.676$) admitted that the desire to sell and earn more profit was the major factor influencing hawking on the Campus. Again respondents ($m=3.18$, $\pm SD=1.03$) accepted that waste from their activities are mostly dumped in the streets creating a lot of filth with sachet water rubbers forming a greater part. The study proposes that the campus security should be well equipped to enforce to the letter existing rules and regulations on selling in

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unauthorized areas and students should be sensitised on the dangers of entertaining hawkers and consuming their goods. The study also recommended that mini markets should be set up in areas where students normally patronize hawkers wares.

Keywords: Street vendors/hawkers; hawking activities; educational institution; Kumasi Campus.

1. INTRODUCTION

Street vending or hawking is increasingly becoming an option for people in most third world countries. According to [1], with the many transformations that have emanated through civilization engendered by education, the age long practice of hawking in major cities and towns is still sustained. Throughout the world, research has shown that varying factors affect the decision of a person to enter into hawking, principal among them are poverty, unemployment, low level of education, low level of entrepreneurial education, non-enforcement of city authority bye-laws, status, migration [2-5]. Their availability along streets, pavements, markets, schools, car parks has raised significance of their contribution to the urban economy but is often overlooked by policy makers [2]. By locating at public places without permission and contributing immensely to filth, street vending or hawking has become a source of city centre's nuisance, a menace as well as an eyesore. Street vending has been held not to be in accordance with acceptable standards and perceived as an affront to existing urban laws and regulations [6,7]. Efforts aimed at evicting street hawkers from the streets and other public spaces by city authorities have resulted in conflict leading to harassments and arrests as well as confiscation of their goods. According to [7], hawkers always adopt spatial strategies by relocating to other places where they can still ply their trade without harassment from authorities. The problem of hawking on the streets and other public space have not only hit major cities in Nigeria [4], Kenya [5], Bangladesh [2], Malawi [8], Ghana [9] but in religious places, schools, offices, bus or railway terminals [2,5]. In this study, the terms 'street vendor' and 'hawker' have the same meaning and would be used interchangeably.

1.1 Research Problem

The immediate problem currently calling the attention of Management of the Kumasi Campus of University of Education, Winneba is hawking at unauthorized places, a situation which is

inimical to teaching and learning in a higher education environment. This relates to the persistent concentration of hawking activities on most parts of the campus including offices, lecture halls, leisure areas, along the streets, pavements etc and its effects on the environment. Prior research has focused primarily on hawking activities and their effects on streets, walkways and other public spaces in the central business district in major cities and towns in Bangladesh [2]; Ghana [9]; Kenya [5]; Malawi [8]; Nigeria [4]. Few studies have focused on the socio-economic impact of relocation on hawkers [10] as well as the effects of street vending on academic performance of in-school children involved in hawking at traffic light intersections [11]. Efforts at curbing hawking have also always concentrated on how city authorities can enforce policies and regulations to see the eviction of hawkers and decongest streets and pavements in the central business districts [7]. Although studies have shown that hawking occurs in religious places, schools, offices, bus or railway terminals [2,5] but factors influencing hawking in such places and the mode of operation of the hawkers as well as the hawking implications have not been empirically assessed hence the need to investigate the activities of hawkers and their implications on an educational institution such as the Kumasi Campus of University of Education, Winneba.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

- Investigate factors influencing hawking on the Campus
- Examine the mode of operation of the hawkers
- Examine the implications of hawking activities on the Campus environment

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Street vending or hawking according to [3] is the act of canvassing for sale of items by hawkers along the street, from house to house or in public places in town. It is characterized by the

organization of businesses with limited educational and professional training, in areas classified as public spaces originally unintended for trading purposes [7,12]. For the purposes of this study and as reiterated by [13], street vendors or hawkers may be stationary in the sense that they occupy space on the pavements or other public/private spaces or they may be mobile in the sense that they move from place to place carrying their wares on push carts or in baskets on their heads. According to [14], street vendors are composed of diverse groups that operate at different stages of business development. To [14], they can be from underprivileged group, unemployed workers from the formal sector, students who see this as a positive work or second generation street vendor. Although studies have shown that most hawkers are between the ages of 20 and 50 years, with few traders falling below 20 years and above 50 years but women dominate the hawking business [5]. Trading activities of hawkers occur in different parts of the urban landscape but hawking sites selection have been based on locations with heavy human and vehicular traffic [9]. Similarly, [15] have also pointed out that hawkers are attracted to areas where there are a large number of consumers for their wares. However, [16] in his study observed that apart from availability of customers at a particular location, the availability of access road and the lack of suitable alternative sites also influence the decision of the hawker in site selection. Although hawking activities seemed to take place throughout the day but [9] have pointed out that hawking has its peak period which is synonymous with human and vehicular traffic peak periods. In their study, they established that the morning peak period was usually between 7am and 10 am while that of afternoon and the evening between 1pm and 3pm, 5pm and 8pm respectively. The increase in hawking activities on the streets and walkways of major towns and cities have been attributed to poverty, unemployment, low level of education, non-enforcement of city authority bye-laws, low level of entrepreneurial education, and unavailability of space in the market [2,3,5,17,18]. Studies have shown that hawkers trade in a variety of commodities such as fruits and vegetables, cereals, fish and meat products, processed food products, cosmetics, second hand clothes, plastic products [5,9] but they are classified differently based on their legality, mobility and level of transience [14]. In their study, [2] classified hawkers in the Dhaka City into four (permanent, semi-permanent, semi-mobile, and

mobile) and indicated that all types of hawkers were available in nearly every area that was studied. [12] on the other hand classified hawkers in the Kumasi City into two (sedentary and footloose) with the sedentary hawkers working in fixed locations while the footloose move throughout the city centres carrying their goods in their hands, on their heads, on push-carts in search of customers. Meanwhile [14] observed that street vendors are not a homogeneous group but are composed of various sectors such as fixed-stall vendors who operate in front of their house or from the street pavement and mobile sellers who wander to different places by carrying their wares by hand or on a push cart. Hawking activities have been identified to produce some amount of garbage in the environment. According to [19] the amount of garbage that hawkers produce is not in small amounts and can give bad effect to the environment with its unpleasant panorama. Similarly, [12] have also pointed out that trading on the streets and pavements has not only created filth but also exacerbated environmental problems, such as traffic congestion, air and noise pollution and poor sanitation, which cause health hazards. According to their study the makeshift structures of the hawkers do not only mar the urban environment and degrade the aesthetic quality of urban settlements but produce pick-pockets and cause stress to pedestrians. [10] in his study revealed that hawkers themselves acknowledged that selling on the streets was not only bad leading to choked drains and disposal of garbage in unauthorized places but also dangerous making it impossible for pedestrians to cross the road. It is expected that hawkers move into markets or stop operating illegally, but this expectation has not been fulfilled [5]. [6] has alluded to the fact that most urban authorities have no consistent policies and regulations applying to street vendors and continue to view their activities as a nuisance, a menace and an eyesore.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Research Design

A descriptive study design was adopted by the researcher since the data collected was quantitative in nature and involves the collection of information from a sample of individuals through their responses to questions [20]. The descriptive study design which always attempts to answer 'what if' questions according to [21], have population validity since the assessment of

attributes of the population is accurate and findings can be generalized [22]. It is also easier and less expensive compared to observation and experimental methods [23].

3.2 Study Population

The target population was all sellers involved in hawking on the Kumasi Campus of University of Education, Winneba. However it was not possible for us to contact all of them within the period set for obtaining data for the study. Sixty (60) of these hawkers were eventually sampled out of all the hawkers in the study area.

3.3 Data Collection Instruments and Procedures

Data for this study were collected from both primary and secondary sources. This was coupled with direct observation and questionnaire administration. Pre-testing of questionnaires was initially conducted using eight (8) randomly selected hawkers operating on the Kumasi Campus of the University of Education, Winneba. Their results were analysed to effect necessary corrections on the final questionnaire used for the study. The final questionnaires were administered to 60 respondents who were selected randomly to obtain information on the characteristics of the respondents, mode of operation, factors influencing hawking and the implications of hawking on the environment. The questionnaire, which contained both open-ended and closed ended questions, was divided into three sections based on the objectives of the study. Objective 1 (Factors influencing hawking on Campus) was evaluated using six items and rated on a 5-points likeness scale (ie strongly disagree to strongly agree); objective 2 (mode of operation of the hawkers) was assessed from three perspectives – categories of items sold, hawking period and hawking sites; objective 3 (implications of hawking activities) was evaluated in three areas: repercussions of hawking activities (four items rated on a 5-points likeness scale of strongly agree to strongly disagree), kinds of filth (six items rated on a 5-points likeness scale of strongly agree to strongly disagree), and discarding of rubbish (five items rated on a 5-points likeness scale of strongly agree to strongly disagree). The questionnaire was self administered but we bore it in mind that some of our respondents may not be able to fill the questionnaire legibly and accurately, hence, we asked them the questions in the questionnaire and assisted them by transcribing

their responses into the questionnaire. The secondary data included data gathered from journal articles, working papers, research reports, conference proceedings and internet sources. These data provided background information about issues of hawking relevant to the study. In terms of direct observation, the researchers observed in an open non-participant role, the issues of hawking which had important relations to the study. This was conducted by interpreting and quantifying through brief on-the-spot notes compiled during data collection exercises by the researcher. The reliability of the scales or test items was determined using cronbach's alpha method. Cronbach's alpha is a measure used to assess the reliability or internal consistency of a set of scale or test items. If the results is generally above alpha value of 0.5 (50%), then it is considered to be reliable [24]. Analysis of the test items on the instrument for the pilot test produced an internal consistency of approximately 73% ($\alpha=.727$). Further analysis of the final instrument used for the study provided an internal consistency of approximately 87% ($\alpha=.868$) which is an improvement over the pilot test. This suggesting that there is a relatively higher chance that should the test items be administered again, we are likely to obtain the same or close to the same range of responses.

3.4 Data Analyses

Data obtained from the field were analysed through descriptive statistics (frequency, means and standard deviation to summarise variables). Respondents sampled for the study consisted of 19(32%) males and 41 (68%) females. Respondents were generally young and within the active work group. Majority (n=22, 37.3%) of the respondents were aged 25 – 30 years whilst 16(27%) were aged below 20 years. Only 9(15%) of the respondents were 31 years and above. Concerning the educational level of respondents; the outcome showed that more than half (n=34, 63%) of the respondents had basic education as their highest level of education attained. However, just about a third (n=18, 33%) of the respondents had no formal education (Table 1).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Factors Influencing Hawking on Campus

With regards to factors influencing hawking on the Campus, responses in Table 2 revealed that most hawkers sell in unauthorized places

because of the desire to sell more and earn more profit. This option received the highest mean rating ($m=4.50, \pm SD=.676$) hence ranked first on the mean ranking table. That notwithstanding, the ease of getting students to buy their products also obtained the second highest mean score ($m=4.45, \pm SD=.675$) coupled with unwillingness of students to walk to the market ($m=3.49, \pm SD=.972$) as well as leniency of security personnel ($m=22.2, \pm SD=.589$). The present finding showed that restrictions in the market ($m=2.03, \pm SD=.615$) as well as difficulty in getting a space in the market ($m=2.05, \pm SD=.746$) were in no way factors contributing to hawking on the Campus. The finding implies that the resistance and return of hawkers to the Campus after being driven away by the Campus Security is motivated by profit motive. The desire to sell more and earn more profit as well as other factors as revealed by the present finding are influencing hawking on the Campus contrary to reports by other studies [2,3,5,17]. The finding has proven further that hawkers are attracted to areas where there is a large number of consumers for their wares [9,15]. However, contrary to report by [18] restrictions and lack of space in the market scarcely influence hawking activities on the Campus.

4.2 Mode of Operation of Hawkers

4.2.1 Categories of items sold by hawkers

Analysis of the results indicated 18 (30%) respondents believed that sachet water was the item mostly sold by hawkers on the Campus. Additionally, about a quarter of the respondents ($n=9, 15\%$) stated that hawkers sold shoes and dresses. However, it is worth noting that cooked food was the least hawked item on the Campus (Table 3). It was also observed that the hawkers were not stationed at a particular place but

moved around from one place to the other to sell their wares. Contrary to reports by [2,7,14,25] the present finding suggests that only one category of hawkers operate on the Campus and they are those who move around from place to place carrying their wares in search of customers to sell items like sachet water, fruits, pastries. Although studies have shown that hawkers in the city centres trade in various categories of goods [26-28], but the present finding gave a different view. The present finding showed that hawkers operating in educational institutions with majority of their customers mainly students are highly limited in the kinds of goods they sell.

Table 1. Distribution of sample according to background characteristics

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	19	31.7
Female	41	68.3
Age		
Below 20 years	16	27.1
20 – 24 years	12	20.3
25 – 30 years	22	37.3
31 and above	9	15.3
Educational level		
Basic	34	63.0
Secondary	1	1.9
Tertiary	1	1.9
No formal education	18	33.3

4.2.2 Hawking periods

Hawking periods is one of the factors used by the researcher to measure mode of operation of the hawkers. Results in Fig. 1 showed that hawking

Table 2. Factors influencing selling outside the new market

Factors	Percent (%)					Mean	±SD
	1	2	3	4	5		
Desire to sell more and earn more profit	1.7	-	-	43.3	55.0	4.50	.676
Ease of getting students to buy your products	1.7	-	-	48.3	50.0	4.45	.675
Unwillingness of students to walk to the market	3.4	16.9	13.6	59.3	6.8	3.49	.972
Leniency of security personnel	3.4	76.3	15.3	5.1	-	2.22	.589
Difficulty in getting a space in the market	11.7	81.7	-	3.3	3.3	2.05	.746
Restrictions in the market	8.5	86.4	-	3.4	1.7	2.03	.615

1= Strongly disagree; 2=Disagree; 3=Neutral; 4=Agree; 5=Strongly agree

has its peak period. About two-thirds (n=41, 74%) of the hawkers indicated that they embark on their hawking activities especially in the afternoon. It also became evident that some amount of hawking (n=9, 16%) took place in the evening. However less hawking activities (n=5, 9%) was seen to take place in the morning suggesting that most hawkers do not start hawking early [5] because the few students available in the morning are preoccupied with lectures and only buy in the afternoon. The present finding is similar to [1]. In their study regarding sachet water hawking and environmental effects in Ikeja, Lagos, it was established that hawking activities takes place throughout the day with the peak period in the afternoon between 12noon and 4.59pm.

4.2.3 Hawking sites on campus

From the survey, it was gathered that the bulk of hawking activities on the Campus took place on the stretch of road leading to the Faculty Block. This obtained a mean score of (m=1.03, ±SD=.158) hence ranked first among the list of places on the campus considered as hawking sites. Additionally, the Opoku Ware II Hall (m=1.05, ±SD=.226), TL Blocks (m=1.04, ±SD=.189), Around New Auditorium (m=1.06, ±SD=.242) and Atwima Hall (m=1.07, ±SD=.267) were also considered as hawking sites where these hawkers normally ply their trade. However,

the results showed that the Car Park (m=1.50, ±SD=.548) is the least hawked area on the Campus. It was observed that the road to the Faculty Block, Opoku Ware II Hall and TL Blocks were mostly filled with students trooping in and out of lecture halls thereby drawing hawkers to these areas to sell their wares. The present finding is similar to what was reported by [9,15,29] that hawkers always locate themselves at strategic places where there is heavy human traffic and where they can be seen by pedestrians and motorists. However the findings were contrary to what was reported by [5] that hawkers prefer to hawk in between moving vehicles in traffic and street pavement in order to enjoy high patronage.

Table 3. Categories of items sold by hawkers

Categories of item sold	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Sachet water	18	30.0
Fruit	7	11.7
Rubbers products	7	11.7
Cosmetics	2	3.3
Shoes/dresses	9	15.0
Canned drinks	4	6.7
Jewellery	6	10.0
Bread / Pastries	6	10.0
Cooked food	1	1.7

Fig. 1. Periods hawking activities take place

4.3 Implications of Hawking Activities on the Environment

4.3.1 Repercussion of hawking activities

With regards to the opinion of hawkers concerning filth, congestion, distraction of lectures and students' learning, the survey results showed that filth (m=3.75, ±SD=.452) obtained the highest mean score whereas the distraction of lectures and students' learning also turned out to be the second highly rated perceived effects of the hawking activities by hawkers. That notwithstanding, a significant number of respondents also believed that the menace creates congestion on the Campus. It, however, obtained the least mean score of (m=2.03, ±SD=.561) (Table 4). The present finding is similar to that of [5] who reported in his study on street hawking and its impact on Nairobi central business urban space that 62% of hawkers admitted that street hawking activities causes a lot of filth. Reports by [10,12] have also supported the present finding to the effect that hawkers activities do not only create filth but congestion as well.

4.3.2 Kinds of filth created

Probing further into the kind of filth hawkers perceived to be created by their activities on the

Campus, the results revealed that 'sachet water rubbers' obtained the highest mean score of (m=4.17, ±SD=.418) as well as wrappers with the second highest mean score of (m=3.92, ±SD=.497). However, filth from boiled foods obtained low rating (m=2.43, ±SD=.789) (Table 5). The present finding is similar to [5] who reported that sachet water rubbers and biscuits rappers were among hawkers items that lead to generation of filth on the streets. The finding also suggests that sachet water sellers hawk on the campus more than any other kind of hawkers which is then followed by biscuits sellers. The rule of thumb is that most of the sachet water sellers sell other items (confectionaries) in addition to the sale of sachet water.

4.3.3 Areas where filth from hawkers activities are discarded

Concerning where the sachet water rubbers and other garbage from the hawking activities were disposed off, streets/roads on the Campus obtained the highest mean score of (m=3.18, ±SD=1.03) while lecture halls also received the second highest mean score of (m=2.97, ±SD=1.04) as the places where students dump waste. However, the respondents disagreed that (m=2.22, ±SD=.585) the consumers discard garbage in the flower gardens on the Campus.

Table 4. Hawking sites on campus

Mode of operation	Percent			
	1	2	Mean	±SD
Car Park	50.0	50.0	1.50	.548
Offices/Administration block	75.0	25.0	1.25	.452
In front of Franky Jay	85.7	14.3	1.14	.378
In front of the market	87.5	12.5	1.13	.354
Autonomy Hall	88.9	11.1	1.11	.323
Atwima Hall	92.9	2.5	1.07	.267
Around New Auditorium	93.9	6.1	1.06	.242
Opoku Ware II Hall	94.7	5.3	1.05	.226
TL Blocks	93.9	6.1	1.04	.189
Road to Faculty Block	97.5	2.5	1.03	.158

1= Yes, 2=No

Table 5. Repercussions of hawking activities

Implication	Percent (%)					Mean	±SD
	1	2	3	4	5		
Filth	5.0	6.7	1.7	81.7	5.0	3.75	.856
Distraction of lectures	8.5	83.1	3.4	5.1	-	2.05	.570
Disruption of student learning	8.5	81.4	6.8	3.4	-	2.05	.539
Congestion	8.6	84.5	1.7	5.2	-	2.03	.561

1= Strongly disagree; 2=Disagree; 3=Neutral; 4=Agree; 5=Strongly agree

Table 6. Kinds of filth

Filth	Percent (%)					Mean	±SD
	1	2	3	4	5		
Sachet water rubbers	-	-	1.7	80.0	18.3	4.17	.418
Biscuits rappers	-	3.3	6.7	85.0	5.0	3.92	.497
Sweets rappers	-	5.0	6.7	85.0	3.0	3.87	.536
Fruits	-	5.0	11.7	80.0	3.3	3.82	.567
Canned / bottled drinks	3.3	18.3	21.7	56.7	-	3.32	.892
Boiled foods	5.0	60.0	21.7	13.3	-	2.43	.789

1= Strongly disagree; 2=Disagree; 3=Neutral; 4=Agree; 5=Strongly agree

Table 7. How hawkers and consumers discard rubbish

Consumer discard	Percent (%)					Mean	±SD
	1	2	3	4	5		
Streets / Road	3.3	35.0	1.7	60.0	-	3.18	1.033
Lecture halls	5.0	40.0	8.3	46.7	-	2.97	1.041
Verandas	3.3	45.0	16.7	35.0	-	2.83	.960
Gutters	5.0	48.3	15.0	31.7	-	2.73	.972
Flower garden	3.3	18.3	21.7	56.7	-	2.22	.585

1= Strongly disagree; 2=Disagree; 3=Neutral; 4=Agree; 5=Strongly agree

The results point out that consumers mostly dump refuse on the streets and dirty the lecture halls with the items they buy from the hawkers since they are bought close to these areas.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Hawking activities and their implications on the Kumasi Campus of University of Education, Winneba are almost the same thing as being experienced in the central business district of major towns and cities in some developing countries except that hawkers are limited in the categories of goods they sell and are motivated to sell as a result of the profit motive as well as availability of consumers. However this activity by hawkers selling in unauthorized locations is not only inimical to teaching and learning but undermining the authority of the University to sell only in the centralized market. With the resilience and resistance exhibited by the hawkers not to trade in the centralized market and also in line with objective 2 of the [30], to improve upon the teaching and learning environment, the following recommendations are made. The existing rules and regulations on selling in unauthorized areas on the campus should be strictly enforced to the letter and culprits severely punished to deter other people from engaging in hawking. Students and other members of the University should be sensitized on the dangers of entertaining

hawkers and consuming their goods. The Campus Security should be well equipped to intensify patrols and notices placed at vantage areas on the campus to caution hawkers on illegal trading in unauthorized area. It is highly recommended that mini markets should be set-up in area where students normally patronize hawkers wares.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Author has declared that no competing interests exist.

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